

Self-reflections of Psycho-therapists on their Own Process of Growth and Development

Saman Hakim and Parisha Jijina

Department of Psychology, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara, Gujarat

There has been a need for professional reflection and development at all career stages, Psychotherapists in India typically have limited occasion for self-reflection and discussion of their experiences with professional peers. There has been very limited research being done on the growth and development of a Psycho-therapist in Indian context. Qualitative research design was employed and Interview schedule was prepared. The sample consisted of 10 Clinical Psychologist/Therapists from Vadodara, Ahmedabad, and Gandhinagar with a minimum of ten years work experience. Thematic analysis was used for analyzing the data. The main themes which are elaborated on are: 1) The importance and developmental process of Empathy among the Psychotherapists 2) The development of Non-judgemental Attitude, 3) Personal growth of the psycho-therapists 4) Professional growth of the psycho-therapists, 5) Any spiritual belief that guide them in therapeutic work 6) Mental health practice that help the therapists to prevent mental fatigue and breakdown. The findings of the study are discussed in light of recent literature as well as the researcher's reflexivity in the process of conducting the research. The expert's insights elaborated in the paper will be beneficial for the training of future therapists.

Keywords: Psycho-therapist's growth, psycho-therapist's development, empathy, and mental fatigue

The practice of psychotherapy can be deeply meaningful and rewarding for the therapist (Guy, 1987; Skovholt & Ronnestad, 1992), although therapists are generally happy, healthy, and content with their work (Radeke & Mahoney, 2000), they also encounter considerable challenges when interacting with clients (Kihlburg, Nathan, & Thoreson, 1986; Mahoney, 1997; Schwebel, Schoener, & Skorina, 1994). Challenges, strains, and burdens inherent in therapeutic work need to be recognized, understood, and mastered if therapists are to develop optimally and maintain a positive morale in their work (Orlinsky et al., 1999; Orlinsky et al., 1999).

Throughout the history of psychotherapy, the relationship (also referred to as the therapeutic alliance, working alliance, and collaborative alliance) between therapist and client has been examined and explored many times over. Freud, was one of the first to address the concept that the client is an active collaborator in the treatment process (Copper & Lesser, 2011). Bordin also agreed with Freud, viewing the relationship built, and the collaboration between therapist and client as, "one of the keys, if not the key, to the change process" (Cooper & Lesser, 2011, p. 33).

Empathy and Non-judgmental Attitude

Empathy is a complex multidimensional concept that has moral, cognitive, emotional, and behavioural components (Mercer &

Reynolds, 2002). Empathy means that one understands the ideas expressed, as well as the feelings that are present in the other person. Empathy signifies a central focus and feeling with and in the client's world. In the practice of psychotherapy or counselling, empathy is an essential ingredient in a therapeutic relationship both for the better-functioning client and for the client who functions at a more primitive level.

Unconditional Positive Regard is a central concept in the theories of Rogers, both for psychotherapy and for interpersonal relations. A universal need for positive regard by others appears at about the same time a person begins to experience awareness of self (Rogers, 1959). In therapy, it is a quality of the therapist's experience toward the client. Rogers acknowledged an undesirable connotation of his term 'unconditional positive regard'. It suggests an all-or-nothing condition. However, for the effective therapist, Rogers said it probably occurs sometimes and not at other times, and to varying degrees.

Growth of the Psycho-therapist

Undoubtedly one of the most commonly asked questions of trainee therapists is:

"What personal qualities do you have that will make you a good therapist?" Apart from cliché answers such as *I want to help people* and *I have always been a good listener*, there is a need to look at what personal strengths and weaknesses impact upon our work with clients. It has long been recognised that one's personal attributes affect not only one's work with clients but also one's own personal and professional development (Rogers, 1961).

Indeed in recent years even therapeutic models, which in the past have placed little importance on the client-patient relationship, are now emphasising the value of personal attributes (McLeod, 1998). It has been suggested that the most important element in counselling is the 'personhood' of the counsellor. A central developmental task for most experienced professionals is to create a counselling/therapy role which is highly congruent with the individuals' self-perceptions

Author Note

Saman Hakim, Department of Psychology, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara, Gujarat

Dr. Parisha Jijina, Department of Psychology, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara, Gujarat

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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to

Dr. Parisha Jijina, Department of Psychology, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara, Gujarat

E-mail: jijina.parisha-psy@msubaroda.ac.in

(including values, interests, attitudes), and which makes it possible for the practitioner to apply his/her professional competence in an authentic way. Major sources of influence that were found to influence professional development theories/research, clients, professional elders (professor/ supervisors/mentors/therapists), peers/colleagues, one's own personal life, and the social/cultural environment continue to play an important role for the professional functioning and development of the experienced professional. As previously described, counsellors /therapists reports that interpersonal experiences impact them strongly throughout their career. With increasing experience, however, this is even more the case. Specifically, the experienced professional reports that much learning comes from their direct experience with clients and from their personal life (Rønnestad & Skovholt, 2003).

Method

The study primarily aims to understand the process of growth and development of the Psycho-therapist in Indian context.

Participants

Since the study focuses on the growth and development of a Psycho-therapist, Purposive Sampling technique and Snowball Sampling technique and was employed to identify the experienced experts. The sample consisted of 10 experts in the field of Psychotherapy with minimum of ten years of experience in their Clinical and Therapeutic practice. The data was collected from three cities that is Ahmedabad, Gandhinagar and Vadodara city. The experts were working in Government hospitals/ Educational Institution/ Private practice.

Measure

Basic socio-demographic details sheet had been given which included Name, Years of Experience, Specialization, and Research areas.

An Expert interview schedule was prepared based on the objectives of the study. The questions were open-ended allowing the experts to elaborate and share their experience, which was then validated by two professors of Psychology.

Expert Interview is defined as, "Expert interviews are where the interviewees are of less interest as whole person than their capacities as experts for certain field of activity (Flick, 2009).

Plan of Analysis

The present research uses broad Thematic based content analysis.

Results

The following themes were found in understanding the importance and development of empathy in the therapist.

The meaning empathy holds for the experts:

All the ten expert's responses when defining empathy were broadly the same: "*Empathy is, understanding the client's emotions and feelings and being in the shoes of others and knowing where it pinches*" and also that it is an innate quality within us and it is one of our personality characteristics.

Further the experts have elaborated meaning which share the same theme according to their following views:

"Stepping into the shoes of another person and understanding, basically how he is feeling, how he is thinking, what is he/she going through, what are his/her emotions that is empathy".

Empathy is an important characteristic of a psychotherapist because if empathy is not there the person is not able to connect to the client and that would be more helpful in longer term in understanding the mental illness and the client".

When asked about the individual characteristics, one expert reported that *Empathy is the most basic characteristics, without this you cannot proceed further in your psychotherapy.* Whereas the other experts reported their explanation as follows: "*In psychotherapy you have to better understand the mental condition of the client as well as their characteristics and empathy plays an important role, only if you understand the feeling then you can start psychotherapy in right manner.*"

Another expert reported "*The individuals are born with personality characteristics but a lot of personality characteristics are invented and shaped over a period of time*", "*As an individual characteristics of empathy, when you accept your client as he/she is without any pre-conceived notions or post delayed responses you exactly embrace the person as he/she is irrespective of what he/she is going through.*" The remaining experts responded to question to being same as their definition given to empathy.

For the role of empathy in therapeutic practice one expert reported, "*Empathy is the basic step to start with, and it basically helps to understand to client and then the client also starts believing or trusting that I am at a right place and therapist understands me and while understanding, therapist can help to come out form the problem.*" Another expert reported "

One expert reported "*Right from the first contact that we maintain with client to listen to their set of problems and how do you go about, empathy starts from there and when it comes to life therapy empathy is 24x7 job without empathy you cannot do anything, it is the empathy which actually defines all other living experiential components for the therapist to carry his/her therapeutic practice.*" Whereas the rest of the seven experts did not respond to the question.

Development of Empathy

When it comes to training, eight experts have taken training either during their academic course that is in their Masters degree or M.Phil program, or through some other training programme that is one expert reported, "*Undergoing psychotherapeutic training for supportive psychotherapy and individual psychotherapy where we had to discuss their cases with the supervisor what exactly transpires the therapist and the client in that 45 minutes of a session and that way supervisor would reflect a lot of therapists own things and help in recognising the mistakes and that helped to get insight.*" One expert reported of getting training after her completion of academics where they had case discussions, case presentations as well the observation had to be made in writing and then the supervisor would evaluate. For the development of empathy as per all the experts empathy comes in or develops once you are into the practice and through ones experience and also that it is a day to day experience.

All the experts reported that reading training and life experiences have helped to brought in empathy. For one expert the Rehabilitation Council of India training which had a empathy component as part of their training. One expert reported that teaching her students during their In-house placements lectures gave her the insight about empathy.

One expert reported that she had undergone Red-Cross training through which she learned about empathy. One expert reported that

she had three month training during her post graduation under a psychiatrist in Psychiatry department of Sir Sayajirao General Hospital, Baroda. Rest four expert denied for having any training in development of empathy.

Two experts reported similar response for example, *"It has been 21 years of practice which has helped me through my experience working with the disabled, the specially-able developed more empathy in me."* one expert reported that, *"I don't think it will take years to develop empathy, empathy is the very natural process."* One expert reported, *"It is a day by day training and a day by day experience."* One expert reported, *"For her it was much before she came into Psychology and may be somewhere the kind of exposure that I had from medical background in my own family, I had people my father as a role model exercising empathy as a part of medical practice so home environment did reinforce empathy as practice in my day to day experiences so almost 18 years it took me to understand empathy completely."* Whereas the other five experts did not respond to this question.

All the ten experts have reported that reading and training as well as practical exposure has helped to developed empathy. Where few excerpts show that: one expert reported, *"Reading about different cases and books on Freud's and Jung's concepts as well as from my teachers."* one expert reported, *"Reading and training In-house Placement students and with more and more interaction with the people and clients has helped in developing the skill."* One expert reported, *"Through the various therapies as part of therapy development program and training programme and training sessions, but major contribution has been the cases that I have handling all these years. More challenging case where there have been resistance from the client gave me more confidence to practice empathy"*

The Philosophical/religious/ethical Views in Development of Empathy

Whereas one expert reported that, *"Buddhist Psychology help me a lot in understanding psychology and also Buddhist teachings which has a lot of scientific matter in terms of clarity of concepts, practicality and understanding."* and one expert reported that, *"Indian Psychology which again talks about the human mind and nature, the problems of suffering and why this suffering are there so this kind of knowledge help to understand the client."* And also three of the experts reported that they followed their Ethical values of profession as well as the ethical values that one receives from the family. Three of the experts have denied of any philosophical/religious/ethical views.

Overcoming Difficulties and Challenges in Cultivating Empathy

When facing a difficult situation in having empathy nine experts have reported that they did face difficulty in their initial years of practicing but they could overcome it and learned through their insight and mistakes and as per their current status now, it has been as part of their practice that comes automatically within their practice, whereas one expert did not respond to the question. In the excerpts: one expert reported that, *"In my initial days of practice when she met a special child who did not have hand, then it was difficult for me to know how to go about, I did not understand as to what do I do but I could overcome it."* one expert reported, *"Only with one client when he was not doing his homework and rigid about coming since long that irritated me but then I understood in between and later in*

reflection."

The Non-judgemental Attitude

The Meaning of Non-judgemental Attitude in a Therapeutic Practice

Two expert reported similar responses as the excerpt *"When you take the individual or someone who is very raw that is without being aware about the family background and unknown to you then acceptance increases."* And five of the experts have reported that non-judgemental attitude was there within them as their nature which helped them in their practice. Also one expert reported that when *"I give enough time to the client to share whatever he/she would like to and also more of sharing from the client, higher is the their non-judgemental attitude or no judgemental attitude."* Three of the experts have reported that the non-judgemental attitude had been difficult for them in situations where there was resistance from the clients. Two of the experts reported that initially in their practice they developed a judgemental attitude because of the family background of the client for example one expert reported, *"When a child came to me for psychological assessment I knew that the mother was having a mental illness so the thought came in before testing that, "Mummy aise hai to bachhe me ye problems aayega hi."*

Meaning of Unconditional Positive Regard and its Help in the Therapeutic Practice

When asked about the Unconditional Positive Regard one of the expert has reported that *"Accepting the person as a person irrespective of whatever the issues are bothering him/her"* another expert reported that *"Unconditional positive regard is what a mother gives to her child without expecting anything in return and also accepting the person's mistake and encouraging him/her to do it the right way the next time and this can be practiced with the clients"* and also one expert reported that, *"To extend the love and support for all even if it is not received back"* is unconditional positive regard for her, whereas the rest of eight experts skipped the questions.

Practicing Therapy Enables Personal Growth of the Therapist

The responses received were one expert reported that, *"The more we work with the individuals the more we come closer to them, it helped me in knowing individuals better as each individual is different and because of this it has helped in accepting the differences and helping them out"*. One expert reported, *"Every time the therapist improves in not repeating the same mistakes which they have committed with one client that is how it helps in personal growth."* For two expert practicing therapy has made her more social then earlier, and being strong emotionally .For one expert she has been more accepting, giving and more open to people. one expert reported that practicing therapy has given her the stress management skills, commitment towards her profession and fulfilling her duties on time. For one expert reported, *"I have been a sensitive person to understand sensitivity of people and also I could overcome my weaknesses as well as the emotional quotient has increased."* Three of the experts did not respond to the question.

For any kind of personal growth it is important to undergo experiences and inculcate those new positive things into oneself which becomes an essential part in therapist's life and guides the therapist for a successful journey in the profession.

Professional Growth of the Psycho-therapist

Role of Academia, Associations, Peers, Reading or Training in the up Gradation of the Professional Capacities

The responses were eight experts reported that Reading, Institutions of Academics, Professional group discussions of cases, Training programs and Workshops as well as their practice experiences have contributed in the up gradation of professional capacities. Whereas one expert has reported that for her interns or students has helped her a lot by interacting with them and teaching them therapies. Whereas one expert had shared negative experience that very less of Peer, Associations help in the up-gradation because it also depends on the individual whether to share and discuss the cases with peers as sometimes there is negative feedback from others thus they refrain from sharing their experiences.

For the development as a professional the responses given were one expert reported that profession has helped in development as there has been resourcefulness in her, developed communication skills. One expert reported that practice of therapy and having successful cases has developed her professionally. One expert reported that practicing reading has helped her, she explains by giving a statement, *"When we read every line, each word it changes its meaning when we read the 2nd time, 3rd time and 4th time so in the beginning we make notes for ourselves and underline one line then 4 lines and 2nd time when we read then the remaining lines also get underlined taking it as important and meaningful, thus entire chapter gets underlined same so that any profession also grows."* For one expert practicing therapy of profession has made her more humble and simple. While the rest six expert mentioned that it has been positive for them till now.

The responses obtained from seven experts were common that the learning experience from their practice and their clients have been helpful in the development as a therapist. One expert reported that, *"My practice as well as the professionals and other people around have helped in the development."* Two expert reported similar responses that is, *"Good environment, own understanding about the therapy, looking for newer information and the kind of clients that have been handled over a period of time has contributed and reinforced in the practice."*

Profession plays an integral part in any individual's life and through profession one learns the techniques and ways of making oneself successful and knowledgeable in their work and also helps in the development throughout the practice of their profession.

Spiritual Belief that Guides the Therapists

The response by one expert was Buddhist Psychology has helped her to understand the psychology, in terms of clarity, concepts, practicality applicability and understanding. For one expert, *"Gandhian philosophy has an impact as well as philosophies of Vivekanand and Geeta has guided me in the practice."* Also one expert reported about the quotes that people make does influence her. For one expert *"Indian Philosophy has helped me to understand Psychology better."* One expert reported that, *"Humanism has been one aspect as well basic spiritual and philosophical beliefs has guided me."* Whereas five experts denied of having any spiritual/philosophical/religious beliefs.

A Spiritual/Philosophical belief guides the therapist to understand

the profession better and helps in the encouragement as well as gives the power to get directed in the right direction or on the right path in their practice.

Practices that Help them to Prevent their Mental Fatigue and Burnout

All the ten experts reported that there has been no burnout at all as they enjoy their profession, and among ten, for two experts also reported there had been stress due overburden of work or because of their physical health. And when asked about the maintenance of their positive experience the responses obtained were that through exercise, meditation, being with self completely or engaging in leisure activities and spending time with friends and family or cooking or listening helps them to maintain the positive experiences and remain stress free.

Two experts suggested that *"Come with loads of compassion to do any work and it overwrites everything."* Two experts suggested short listing your goals and taking as much as practical training as one can. Two experts suggested that *"Observe, understand the emotions of the client but do not get carried away by them."* One expert suggested, *"Believe in practical and self exposure, involve yourself in the practice, being aware and re-actualization will help to learn."* One expert suggested, *"Sit and reflect upon yourself and it will automatically give you answers."* Two of the experts suggested that, *"Love thy neighbour as love thyself"* and also love your profession and strengthen your emotions and stay happy. And one expert suggested *"Allow enough space for client, patiently exercise what they have and never look down upon whatever they have in hand and if that's the spirit empathy, unconditional positive regard, aspirations, aims, career goals, personal satisfaction in life everything will take its own beautiful shape. And also working with a missionary approach or missionary thought then you can embrace the component of psychotherapy."*

The burnout and fatigue may not be experienced by the individual if he/she has passion, love and dedication towards his/her work or profession or the therapeutic practice.

Thus through the results show that Empathy, Non-judgemental attitude, Personal growth Professional growth, Spiritual belief/Philosophical beliefs/Religious beliefs and the Burnout and Fatigue all these objectives play an important role in the growth and development of a psycho-therapist throughout the practice as well as contributes in being an effective psychotherapist. And also these can be learned or experienced through the practice as a Psycho-therapist with years of experience in the practice.

Discussion

The findings above suggested that empathy and unconditional positive regard are significant qualities and skills for a psycho-therapist. Research has strongly emphasized the qualities of empathy, and non-judgemental stance as the key context that takes therapy forward (Bråten, 2007). The therapeutic alliance built on the foundations of empathy and unconditional positive regard is conceptualized as an all-encompassing framework for psychotherapy services (Hatcher & Barends, 2006). The participants emphasized self-care for all counsellors and therapists. Research has found that therapists are at risk for occupationally related psychological problems such as secondary trauma, anxiety and depression; and self-care in the form of meditation, mindfulness is

significant for the therapists' mental health for sustaining in this profession (Dorian & Killebrew, 2014).

Spiritual beliefs from Buddhism, Shrimad Bhagavad Gita have influenced the therapists in their therapeutic work. Grimm (1994) reported that therapist spiritual values can contribute to therapy, and the goal of effective treatment should be the integration and accommodation of the spiritual and religious needs of both client and therapist. Misra (1996) observed that Western Psychological methods subscribe to an emphasis on individualism, mechanism, and objectivity. Understanding the problems of non-Western cultures through this lens has a debilitating effect in terms of misconstruing their realities. Psychology in India can find its roots in its native wisdom, instead of borrowing knowledge from the West. Indian scriptures dating back thousands of years extensively dealt with the rich and in-depth analysis of states of consciousness and the mind, to help individuals in their pursuit of self-realization. The emphasis of the scriptures was on exploring the 'world within' to alleviate suffering. Indian scriptures have been considered an essential part of Svadhaya or self-learning and have successfully guided generations of knowledge seekers. Thus, they can be viewed as a knowledge mine to guide the modern person through the ebbs and flows of life (Bhawuk, 2010).

The therapists perceived that practicing therapy over the years has contributed to their personal evolution and growth. They perceived themselves as more open, and accepting individuals, with deeper self-awareness and sensitivity towards others. In a study by Bhola et al. (2012) 24% of the therapists reflected on their personal attributes which functioned as professional strengths such as humour, patience, flexibility and the responses also responses focused on the anchoring provided by their spiritual beliefs and practices. The participants suggested that over the years their professional development was facilitated by learning through their clients, their students, and from peers. According to Orlinsky and Ronnestad (2005), therapists endorsed their practical experiences with clients as the most learning influence. Duncan (2010) suggested that therapists are able to progress professionally through gaining feedback from their clients of the services they provide and through maintaining boundary regulations with the clients and mentoring by other professionals (Skovholt & Ronnestad, 1992).

In summary, the senior therapists emphasized the significance of cultivation of empathy and non-judgemental stance, of self-care and maintaining one's emotional hygiene and the anchoring role of spiritual beliefs in therapy. The practices for professional growth suggested were learning from clients, learning from supervisees and students, case discussion with peers and remaining abreast with continuous learning and upgradation of one's skill-set. Over the course of time, perceived strengths and growth as a therapist reported were higher emotional quotient, better communication skills and developing enhanced skills of openness and acceptance.

Implications of the Study

- The therapists' suggestions based on their vast practical experience will be beneficial for the professional development of counsellors, psychologists and therapists in India, and learning about the experiences of senior therapists, may prepare the younger therapist better for their own professional journey
- The strategies suggested by the experts for self-care may be utilized as a preventive measure by the young trainee therapists to

prevent burn-out and fatigue.

- The findings of the study may be useful for supervisors and mentors to guide their supervisees and contribute towards therapy education in India.

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